

Perception of Climate Effects on Agriculture by Farmers in Damaturu Metropolitan, Yobe State

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ABSTRACT

The farmer's adaptation decision to cope with the effects of climate change has drawn considerable attention and recognition of the local and global scale's human-environmental approach. In this paper, we tried to understand the human dimension of adaptation decision of farmers in Damaturu metropolitan. We analyze the farmer's perception of climate change effects and socio-economic determinants of farm household which influence adaption decisions and adaptation strategies choices. We conducted a micro-level assessment of 246 farmers and farm households in Damaturu metropolitan, Yobe state of Nigeria. The data is analyzed through descriptive statistics methods and logistic regression. The study finds out that 80 per cent of the surveyed farmers in the study area perceive and predict climate changes effects and choose to adopt. This study found that the key socio-economic variables such as the farmer's age, gender, household size, education level, off-farm income, and farm-size influence farmers' adaptation decision and outcome in the study area. This study will help identify the critical household characteristics that may be integrated into future policy formulation and implementation to be integrated into future policy formulation and a successful adaptation future. Farmers in the study area are fully aware of the effect of climate change and are also aware of the possible coping strategies such as the need for agricultural insurance, planting of drought and flood tolerant varieties and reduction of water loss through practices such as mulching and rearing of heat tolerant livestock.

Keywords: Climate, Famers, Agriculture, Perception

INTRODUCTION

Background

Agriculture is one of the sectors most vulnerable to climate change impact in Africa (Falaki et al. 2012). Impact of climate is observed more where agriculture is rain-fed and essential for the daily subsistence such in Nigeria. Across Nigeria, millions of people are already experiencing changing seasonal patterns of rainfall and increased heat. There are projections of increases in rainfall in the humid regions of southern Nigeria, which are accompanied by increases in cloudiness and rainfall intensity particularly during severe storms (Ibebuchi, & Abu, 2023). Similarly, the savannah areas of northern Nigeria were projected to experience less rainfall, which coupled with temperature increases. The country's coastline (about 853 km long) makes the large population of coastal communities vulnerable to increases in sea level and storm surges (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) 2013). Almost two-third of Nigeria's land

cover is prone to drought and desertification (Ahmed, Abba, Siriki, & Maman, 2020). Climate therefore determines to a large extent availability of water, which impacts health and ultimately the level of poverty amongst Nigerians. The country's high population of over 150 million people depend primarily on their physical environment for food, livelihoods and survival. Unfortunately, Nigeria lacks the financial capacity and technological resources to address the postulated negative impacts of current and predicted climate change and has not yet fully established an institutional and legal framework, systematic approach or policies targeted mitigating and adapting to the impacts of climate change. Given the above factors, it is clear that Nigeria's long-term development goal of poverty reduction and economic growth will be severely constrained if insufficient attention is paid to the issue of climate change in Nigeria IPCC (2014). Climate change or global warming has become a new reality, with deleterious effects: seasonal cycles are disrupted, as are ecosystems; and agriculture, water needs and supply,

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and food production are all adversely affected (Upadhyay, 2020). It also leads to sea-level rise with its attendant consequences, and includes fiercer weather, increased frequency and intensity of storms, floods, hurricanes, droughts, increased frequency of fires, poverty, malnutrition and series of health and socio-economic consequences. It has a cumulative effect on natural resources and the balance of nature (Dadzie, 2021). Climate change can be exacerbated by human induced actions such as: the widespread use of land, the broad scale deforestation, the major technological and socioeconomic shifts with reduced reliance on organic fuel, and the accelerated uptake of fossil fuels (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment). The most devastating adverse impacts of climate change in Africa includes frequent drought, increased environmental damage, increased infestation of crop by pests and diseases, depletion of household assets, increased rural urban migration, increased biodiversity loss, depletion of wildlife and other natural resource base, changes in the vegetation type, decline in forest resources, decline in soil conditions (soil moisture and nutrients), increased health risks and the spread of infectious diseases, changing livelihood systems, etc. (Reilly, 2019; Abaje and Giwa, 2017). In many African countries, economies are largely based on weather-sensitive agricultural and forest fruits production systems which are vulnerable to climate change (Aryal, Sapkota, Khurana, Khatri-Chhetri, Rahut, & Jat, 2020). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2014) reported that the Africa region is one of the major areas of the world most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Previous studies have shown that climate change has significant impacts on crop yields (Deressa et al. 2018). Climate change is increasingly one of the most serious national security threats which will have significant impacts on natural resources, ecosystems, and biodiversity, and at

the same time, it is likely to trigger food insecurity and decrease plants' productivity and availability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Damaturu is the capital city of Yobe State, Nigeria, which lies between latitude 11° 39' 30" - 11° 47' 00" N and longitude 11° 54' 00" - 12° 02' 00" E, covering a land area of about 45,502 square kilometers (km²) (Fig.1). Damaturu is in the semi-arid region, with relatively flat terrain. It is a high land which is characterized by sandy plains (Adamu, & Taa, 2022). The annual temperature ranges from 39°C to 40°C with highs between February-May. The rainy season begins in June, with an average rainfall of 649mm which spread up to October, depending on the year and the onset. The vegetation of the area is predominantly Sahelian, consisting of savannah grasslands, scattered shrubs, and acacia trees. The landscape is generally open, with few forests or dense vegetation (Kurowska, Czerniak, & Garba, 2022). The people of the area are predominantly peasant farmers, livestock herders, and traders and produces a wide variety of crops, which include legumes (groundnuts and beans); Cereals (maize, millet, sorghum and rice), solanaceous crops (peppers, tomato, garden eggs) and reared animals like; camel, sheep, goats, and poultry among others. Damaturu local government has a population of about 88,014 in 2006 based on the census of the National Population Commission with a density of about 38 persons per km² (NPC, 2006) and 124,500 with a density of 52.62 persons per km² with Kanuri and Fulani are the two main ethnic groups of Damaturu coexisting with Kare-Kare, Bolewa, Babur, and Bade as well as other non-indigenous tribes.

Figure 1: The Study Area Map.

2.2 Research Design

The research is a cross-sectional survey research design. It is cross sectional study because the data that was collected within a framework time. It is a survey research design because the researcher and field assistant have gone to the field and gather the opinion of the respondents, mostly at the farmers level, on perception of climate effect in agriculture by farmers in Damaturu, Yobe State. Primary data was collected using questionnaire.

2.3 Population for the Study

The population of Damaturu is 124,500 with 54% males and 46% females. The target population of the study are farmers within Damaturu metropolitan.

2.4 Sample Size

The study sample was 11,500 farmers within Damaturu. In order to get a representative sample size for farmers respondents involved in the study, the Cochran (1963:75) formula (4) was adopted.

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where; n= the desired sample size (when population is greater than 10,000 people);

z= the standard normal deviation, usually set at 1.96 which corresponds to the 95 percent confidence level;

p= the proportion in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic set at 0.8;

q= 1.0-p. Thus, q=1.0-0.8= 0.2; and

d= degree of accuracy desired, usually set at 0.05

Substituting these figures into the formula:

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.8)(0.2)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416)(0.16)}{(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{0.614656}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 245.86$$

$$n = 246$$

2.5 Sampling Technique

The random sampling techniques was adopted for the study of farmers in Damaturu Metropolitan.

2.6 Data source and Type

Data collection is the questionnaire tool for the study. The data will be collected through two (2) major sources of data collection, primary and secondary, the primary source is such as field survey, interview,

structured questioners and secondary sources are such as text books, journals, and internet.

through field observation was then be incorporated directly into the research.

2.7 Method of Data Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data collected using questionnaire was analyzed using (descriptive statistics frequency and percentage) bar graph and pie chart while data that was collect

Table 3.1 Farmer’s Perception on Change in Amount of Rainfall

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	229	94
No	17	6
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

rainfall pattern while the remaining 6% know that climate change causes excessive rainfall, prolonged drought, over flooding and erosion.

The result in table 3.1 show that majority (94%) of the farmers describe climate change as a change in

Table 3.2 Timing of the onset of rain in the main season shifted

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	201	81
No	45	19
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

which lead to main season shifted. 81% of the respondents agreed that the timing of the onset rain fall season shifted, while 19% disagreed.

The result in table 3.2 above shows the result on the change of climate lead to timing of the onset of rain

Figure 3.1 Rain Started late than normal

The figure above on the change in climate lead to rain to start late than normal. 81% of the respondent agreed that due to climate change rain started late than

normal while 19% of the respondents said disagreed to the fact that rain started late than normal.

Table 3.3 Temperature of the area is changing

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	227	92
No	19	8
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

decrease or increase; 92% of the respondent agreed that the temperature of the study area is changing while 8% of them did not agree.

Results on the table 3.3 above shows that climate change led to changing in temperature weather

Table 3.4 Decline of Agriculture yields

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	236	95
No	10	5
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

respondents which constitute 95% of the total respondents said Yes while 10 respondents constitute 5% said No. This clearly shows that climate change decline agriculture yields.

The result in table 4.10 above reveals the results of climate change decline of agriculture yields; 236

Table 3.5 Tree Planting Campaigns as Solution of Current Climate Change

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	236	95
No	10	4
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

agreed that tree planting will reduce climate change while 10 respondents which constitute 5% said NO. This clearly indicate that tree planting in one of the strategies of coping climate change and it's very effective.

The result in table 4.11 on weather Afforestation Tree planting campaigns will bring solution to your current climate; 236 respondents which constitute 95% had

Figure 3.2 Increase energy efficacy and use of renewal energy to cope climate change.

The chart above shows results of increase in use of energy efficacy and use of renewal energy will cope climate change. As it can be seen in the chart 146 respondents said yes this will cope climate change

while 100 respondents said No. Based on the majority responds increase energy efficacy and use of renewable energy will be part of strategy to cope with the climate change.

Table 3.6 Use of different crop varieties

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	201	82
No	45	18
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The result in table 3.6 reveals the results of use of different crop varieties as a strategy of coping climate change. 201 respondents which constitute 82% said

yes while 45 respondent which constitute 18% said no. This reveals that use of different varieties of crop in farming also a good strategy in coping climate changes.

Figure 3.3 Short Season Crop Variety.

The pie chart above reveals the results of; using short season crop variety farming as strategies to cope with climate change. As it can be seen in the pie chat 53%

of the respondents said yes this could reduce climate change while 47% did not agreed.

Table 3.7 Early Mature Crop

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	190	77
No	56	23
Total	246	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The results on the table above shows the use early matured crops as a strategy for coping climate in the

study area; 190 respondents which constitutes 77.2% while 56 respondents which constitute 22.8% did not agreed.

Figure 3.4 Source information on climate change by the farmers

Figure 3.4 reveal the source information on climate change by the farmers; as it can be seen in the chart above 50 respondents said it Radio, 32 respondents said Newspaper, 43 respondents said Community informant, and 100 respondents said traditional rulers while 19 respondents said government agencies.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively farmers are fully aware of the effect of climate change and are also aware of the possible coping strategies such as the need for agricultural insurance, planting of drought and flood tolerant varieties and reduction of water loss through practices such as mulching and rearing of heat tolerant livestock. However, farmers did not perceive stoppage the of use of inorganic fertilizer as a coping strategy. Most farmers with low education had high perception of climate change because climate tends to impact more on their crop and livestock production efforts as this is probably the main livelihood sources. That is, farmer's livelihood depends on agriculture and any distortion in its production chain can be responsible for the high farmer's perception of effect of climate change. On the other hand, farmers with high educational level may record low perception due to the fact that they may have other sources of income other than farming. The findings from this study revealed that the majority of the farmers in the study area perceived changes in climatic conditions, whereas only few did not. Almost all farmers reported increases in temperature, droughts, floods, and decreasing the rainfall. Increasing temperature along with decreasing precipitation may enhance the water

scarcity from resulting droughts which will affect crop production. This, in turn, may have a significant contribution to farmers' reducing the risks that they lose against climate change effects.

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